

Supplementary Material

1. Survey*

* The following version is a translation from the original Italian survey. Despite our efforts to follow guidelines for survey translations (e.g. <https://www.ccsgr.isr.umich.edu/index.php/chapters/translation-chapter/translation-overview>) some embedded assumptions may not work in every cultural context, complex words may not have a correspondent translation, and particularities of residency programs in Italy may differ from those in the U.S.A. For these reasons, we have also included a brief description of how Neurology Residency Programs are designed in Italy.

Neurology Residency Programs in Italy: an overview

Neurology Residency Programs (formally called “Neurology Schools”) in Italy are offered by 36 universities and last four years. Residents generally work in University hospitals but rotations in community hospitals are possible. In bigger cities, such as Rome, Milan, and Naples, several hospitals have academic affiliations and provide training opportunities for the residents. Educational goals for trainees are defined by the Ministry of University and Research through national guidelines. Each Neurology Residency program has a Residency Director that coordinates the trainees and plans the activities.

National guidelines emphasize the general educational goals that residents have to achieve at the end of the four years, but each Residency Program Director is independent in organizing trainees’ activity. For instance, rotations in neurophysiology and neurosonology services, neurointensive care and stroke units as well as neuroradiology, neurosurgery, psychiatric and neuropsychiatric wards may vary in duration, year of eligibility and availability of services depending on the university residency program. Particularly, in big cities, residents are trained in many different hospitals and not in one formally appointed center, with different tasks and subspecialties, lacking a homogeneous curriculum. Specific Child Neurology tracks lack. Day and night shifts (if any), on-call services, and daily working time are not strictly regulated, and they do not depend on residents’ seniority. They may also vary widely among programs. Rotations in a minimum number of subspecialty services (e.g. movement disorders; neuromuscular disorders) are not required.

Training abroad is not mandatory, but it is possible in some programs.

Trainees can choose to perform both clinical and basic science research depending on the main research interests at the working Institution. Part of the training (duration not defined) can be dedicated to full-time research activities, usually during the last year of residency.

Didactics is usually provided with in-person frontal lessons. Hours per week dedicated to clinical grand rounds, morning reports, and bedside teaching sessions are not established and vary among programs.

Survey

Dear Colleagues,

We offer you to take part in a survey on the impact of SARS-CoV-2 pandemic on our training as Neurology residents.

SARS-CoV-2 pandemic has caused many changes in our national healthcare system and it has forced a reorganization of our neurology curriculum. Many of us are fighting front line against the coronavirus, our workload has dramatically increased, and our training programs have rapidly changed.

With this survey, we would like to assess how the pandemic has affected your clinical and research training as well as didactics in your institution. In addition, we would like to know your experience on how critical situations – such as the adequate provision of PPE in time of shortages – have been addressed in your case. Our goal is to gather valuable information to help our Residency Program directors, universities, and hospitals to face this challenge at the best of our possibilities.

Participation in this survey is voluntary. You can leave the survey at any moment without providing any explanation. This survey is anonymous and e-mail addresses will not be collected. Response per resident is limited to one. No compensation will be offered.

By continuing from this page, you give consent to participate.

Thank you for your time and help.

Elena Abati, MD and Gianluca Costamagna, MD

Neurology Residents

University of Milan

1. Are you currently enrolled in a Neurology Residency Program? (one possible answer)

- Yes
- No

Section 1. Demographics

2. How old are you?

3. In which Italian region do you work? (one possible answer)

- Valle d'Aosta
- Lombardy
- Piedmont
- Liguria
- Veneto
- Friuli Venezia Giulia
- Trentino Alto Adige
- Emilia Romagna
- Tuscany
- Abruzzi
- Umbria
- Marches
- Lazio
- Campania
- Molise
- Basilicata
- Calabria
- Apulia
- Sicily
- Sardinia

4. In which city do you work?

Section 2. Clinical Training

5. Which has been your main activity since the beginning of your Neurology Residency Program? (more than one possible answer)

- Inpatient services
- Outpatient/other services
- Clinical research rotation
- Basic science research rotation
- Other: _____

6. Which was your main duty when the first case of SARS-CoV-2 was reported in Italy? (one possible answer)

- Inpatient services
- Outpatient/other services
- Full-time research
- Clinical practice or research abroad

7. How has your activity changed during the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic? (one possible answer)

- Neurology services have not changed
- Working time in neurology services in my hospital has been reduced
- Neurology services interrupted by the residency director
- Deployed to a neurology ward in another hospital
- Deployed to a non-COVID, non-neurologic ward
- Deployed to a COVID ward
- Voluntarily moved to a COVID ward
- Other: _____*

*Other was ticked by one respondent: "Research training abroad was suspended".

Section 3. Research training

8. How has your research training changed during the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic? (one possible answer)

- My research activity has increased
- My research activity has not been modified
- My research activity has decreased
- My research activity has been completely interrupted
- I am not involved in research activity

9. In case of a reduction of your research activity, how has it changed? (more than one possible answer)

- Research facilities have been shut down
- Neuroimaging or electrophysiological instrumentations have been used for other purposes
- Personnel (e.g. administrative staff, nurses, technicians) has been reassigned
- Clinical trials have been suspended
- I have less time for research activities
- Other: _____

Section 4. Training abroad

10. Were you performing your clinical or research activity abroad when the first cases of SARS-CoV-2 appeared in Italy? (one possible answer)

- Yes
- No

11. If you answered yes to the previous question, did you have to partially or completely suspend your training abroad due to the pandemic? (one possible answer)

- Yes
- No

12. If you answered yes to the previous question, how? (one possible answer)

- University/hospital has partially suspended the activities, but I keep going to work
- University/hospital has suspended the activities, but I have continued my project with at-distance approaches
- Residency-program director has asked me to suspend my training abroad to help in clinical services.
- I voluntarily suspended my training abroad
- Other: _____

Section 5. Didactics

13. How has your didactic curriculum changed during the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic? (one possible answer)

- Didactics has been suspended
- Didactics has been offered on virtual platforms
- Didactics has been offered regularly
- Didactics was not planned

14. Do you think that the pandemic had or will have an impact on your clinical training? (one possible answer)

- A positive impact
- No impact at all
- A negative impact

15. If you believe it had or will have an impact, why? (more than one possible answer)

- I improved my skills in managing patients with respiratory symptoms
- I improved my skills as a general internist
- The pandemic has reduced the occasions to gain experience as a clinician
- The pandemic has prompted me to study the literature on SARS-CoV-2
- Other: _____

16. Do you think that the pandemic had or will have an impact on your neurology training?

- A positive impact
- No impact at all
- A negative impact

17. If you believed it had or will have an impact, why? (more than one possible answer)

- I improved my skills in managing COVID-patients with neurological symptoms
- I have had more time to study
- I have missed important goals in my neurology training due to the suspension of neurological services
- The pandemic has limited my improvements as a researcher in neurology
- Other: * _____

* Other was ticked by one respondent: "The number of stroke patients I care for increased".

Section 6. Contagion prevention and surveillance

18. Did you have any contact with confirmed SARS-CoV-2 positive cases? (one possible answer)

- Yes
- No

19. If you answered yes to the previous question, how did your hospital/hosting institution reacted? (one possible answer)

- I was asked to start precautionary home isolation regardless of the presence of symptoms
- I was instructed to self-isolate only in case of appearance of SARS-CoV-2-related symptoms
- A nasopharyngeal swab was collected
- Serological analysis was performed
- Hospital/hosting institution did not take any precautionary measures

20. Do you undergo scheduled surveillance nasal swabs (e.g. every three days, every week) in your hospital/hosting institution? (one possible answer)

- Yes
- No
- Only in some wards
- Not applicable

21. If you worked with confirmed SARS-CoV-2 positive cases, did you receive adequate PPE equipment? (one possible answer)

- Yes
- No
- Only in some cases
- Not applicable

22. If you work in a SARS-CoV-2 ward, did you receive any training on patient management and/or the use of ventilation devices? (one possible answer)

- Yes, in SARS-CoV-2 ward
- Yes, using learning platforms
- No, I self-studied the topics
- No
- Not applicable

Figure e1. Demographics of the surveyed Neurology trainees in Italy.

A map of Italy with the number of respondents per region shown using a heat map. The worst hit region in Italy, Lombardy (*), had the most respondents (N = 40).

Figure e2. Preventative measures after contact with a positive case and PPE provision.

Panel A shows indications given by working Institutions after contact with a positive case. Panel B presents the percentage of respondents who received PPE while working with suspected or confirmed SARS-CoV-2 cases.

A

Which measures have been undertaken by your Institution after a close contact with a patient with confirmed positive SARS-CoV-2 infection?

56 responses

B

If you worked with suspected or confirmed SARS-CoV-2 positive cases, did you receive adequate PPE from your Institution?

79 responses

Figure e3. Neurology residents in COVID-19 wards receiving specialized training on case management.

If you work in a COVID-19 unit, have you received any training on patient management and on the use of respiratory equipment?

79 responses

